

Implementation of Secure Session Key and Shared Verification Protocol in IOV Networks

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Abstract - Establishing mutual authentication and secure key exchange is essential for communication networks, especially over untrusted channels such as the internet. This paper presents the MORNeS protocol, which is designed to securely distribute session keys via a mutually trusted authority. The protocol facilitates timely communication between parties without the need for clock synchronization. MORNeS integrates elements of the Needham-Schroeder authentication protocol and a modified version of the Otway-Rees key exchange protocol to achieve both mutual authentication and secure key exchange. In this protocol, the responsibility for acquiring the session key from the authentication server is placed on the receiver. The communication process consists of a sequence of five messages exchanged between the communicating parties and the trusted third party.

Keywords— Key exchange, access key, mutual authentication, Attacks, cryptography, attacker, trusted authority

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital communication setting, abundant computing environments involve communication over insecure channels. Users often conduct computational tasks on personal computers and share them via the internet, contributing to extensive adoption and development of networked and distributed systems. These systems improve functionality and optimize resource utilization, facilitating collaboration and message exchange among various parties such as processes, users, nodes, and terminals. All through this paper, these entities are termed as "correspondents," a term normally used in authentication literature.

The correspondent verifies the validity of the received message to decide the suitable action to be taken. This authentication [1] ensures that the message is newly generated for its proposed purpose by the claiming correspondent [2].

Insecure networks, such as the Internet, there are a number of security challenges such as eavesdropping and unauthorized interruption. These challenges arise due to the decentralized nature of Internet, which consists of several independent networks. Unlike proprietary networks, the sender cannot control the exact path a message takes to reach to its destination. Therefore, the receiving correspondent must detect malicious entities or replayed messages generated in the past. Encryption plays a vital role for securing communications between parties, authorized them to transmit and receive data securely [3].

In networked and distributed systems, authorization of correspondents for network communication is the elementary task. This task is facilitated by authentication protocols, which consist of predefined rules governing the exchange of messages among correspondents. Authentication protocols guarantee secure transmission of confidential information and have been extensively developed and implemented for regulating the flow of information [4-5].

To know the design process of any authentication protocol, a good understanding of fundamental cryptographic systems and their standard terminology is necessary.

To transmit a plain message P securely over a network, it undergoes encryption using algorithms such as DES [6], IDEA [7], AES [8], among others. This process transforms P into cipher text C , making it

meaningless to unauthorized parties monitoring the transmission. The encryption mechanism inputs a parameter known as a key K to convert P into cipher text C .

After the cipher text has been transferred to its intended recipient, they can decrypt it to get the original plaintext. Decryption is done using a decryption key K^{-1} to reverse the encryption process.

II. IOV SECURITY VIA CRYPTOGRAPHY

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III. PROBLEM FORMULATION AND PROPOSED WORK

While individual cryptographers, both amateurs [9,10] and professionals [11], have made modest modifications to the protocols described in [2,3], there has been no reported effort to integrate these techniques into an efficient prototype for secure communication in uncertain network [12].

A. INTERPRETATION OF THE CURRENT SYSTEM

Consider the Needham-Schroeder protocol [2], which employs conventional encryption. In this method, each participant has a secret key shared with the Trusted Authority (TA). To obtain a secret key K_S from the TA and communicate with another participant, SU follows these steps:

The communication starts with SU sending a non-encrypted message to TA as follows:

SU \rightarrow TA : IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}, N_{SU} --(i)

TA then authenticates the identities of SU and IV and retrieves their respective secret keys shared with TA (K_{SU} and K_{IV}). TA sends the message to SU as follows:

TA \rightarrow SU : $[N_{SU}, IF_{IV}, K_S[K_S, IF_{SU}]K_{IV}]K_{SU}$ --(ii)

Since K_{SU} is a secret key shared exclusively between SU and TA, only SU decrypts the message (ii) to obtain the secret key, SU sends this message packet to IV as follows:

SU \rightarrow IV : $[K_S, IF_{SU}]K_{IV}$ --(iii)

IV receives the message in (iii), it decrypts it to obtain the secret key K_S .

To make sure no interruption occurred during the execution of protocol, further steps are conducted for mutual authentication. A nonce, N_{IV} is generated by IV, to protect against potential attacks and sends this message to SU as follows:

IV \rightarrow SU : $[N_{IV}]K_S$ --(iv)

Since only SU and IV possess K_S , SU can authenticate the message originated from IV. The customized message is then sent back to IV as follows:

SU \rightarrow IV : $[N_{IV} - 1]K_S$ --(v)

SU decrypts this message to retrieve the decremented value of nonce.

This ensures the completion of the protocol designed by Roger M. Needham and Michael D. Schroeder, employing symmetric key encryption.

However, Denning and Sacco [13] verified vulnerabilities in the Needham-Schroeder protocol, finding possible compromises of communication keys. On the other hand, Denning and Sacco highlighted risks such as direct revelation of these keys due to system design negligence or flaws.

Both suggested a situation in which an attacker (CA) intercepts whole messages interchanged between SU and IV during steps (iii)-(v) of the Needham-Schroeder protocol discussed earlier. In addition, the intruder got a copy of the secret key K_S . Afterward, the intruder might use this information to mislead IV into believing it is SU as under:

Firstly, CA would replay the message obtained in step (iii) to IV:

$$CA \rightarrow IV : [K_S, IF_{SU}]K_{IV} \quad \text{--(vi)}$$

After receiving this message, IV interprets it as a message initiation from SU and reply to it with a nonce N_{IV} , encrypting it using the K_S key received in the previous step as follows:

$$IV \rightarrow SU : [N_{IV}]K_S \quad \text{--(vii)}$$

The intruder CA intercepts this message before it reaches SU, decrypts it using the stolen K_S , and then impersonates SU's response as follows:

$$SU \rightarrow IV : [f(N_{IV})]K_S \quad \text{--(viii)}$$

Then, CA gains the ability to send deceptive messages to IV, masked them as originating from SU.

Denning and Sacco introduced timestamps to address this issue. They added another field, TS, to communication received in steps (ii) and (iii) of the protocol. The revised protocol then rewritten as follows:

$$SU \rightarrow TA : IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}, TS \quad \text{--(ix)}$$

$$TA \rightarrow SU : [IF_{IV}, K_S, TS[K_S, IF_{SU}, TS]K_{IV}]K_{SU} \quad \text{--(x)}$$

$$SU \rightarrow IV : [K_S, IF_{SU}, TS]K_{IV} \quad \text{--(xi)}$$

Step (iv) and step (v) are not included here which originally intended to stop replay attacks on non-compromised secret keys. Both SU and IV can prove the originality of the messages using the following equation:

$$|\text{Time} - M| < \Delta d_1 + \Delta d_2 \quad \text{--(xii)}$$

where,

Time: time of the native system

Δd_1 : difference between time of native system and server's time

Δd_2 : expected delay time in network

If difference between timestamp TS and the system's clock is less than $(\Delta d_1 + \Delta d_2)$, the protocol is secure against replay attacks.

On the other hand, the use of timestamps may not be universally applicable due to possible issues with clock synchronization, mainly in distributed environments. Terminals lacking local real-time clocks would meet difficulties in communicating through this protocol.

In [13], Otway and Rees introduced a key interchange protocol that relied on a trusted authority for distributing secret keys to communicating parties.

The chain of steps to perform the protocol is as under:

The originator SU sends a message to receiver IV containing an identifier CI for conversation, as well as identifiers for both SU and IV. Additionally, SU includes a nonce N_{SU} encrypted using a secret key K_S that is shared between SU and the trusted authority TA. The structure of the message is as follows:

$$SU \rightarrow IV : CI, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}[N_{SU}, CI, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]K_{TA} \quad \text{--(xiii)}$$

After receiving this message, IV understands that SU wishes to initiate communication and requests a secret session key from SU. IV then sends a message to TA that includes the message took from SU, with an encrypted message via the secret key K_{IV} that has been shared between IV and TA. The structure of IV's message is as follow

$$IV \rightarrow TA : CI, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}[N_{SU}, CI, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]K_{TA}, [N_{IV}, CI, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]K_{IV} \quad \text{--(xiv)}$$

The TA receives the message and decrypts it using the respective keys K_{SU} and K_{IV} . It verifies that the messages constitute a matching pair with identifiers CI, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV} . Upon successful verification, the TA computes a secret session key K_{SU} and sends a response back to IV:

$$TA \rightarrow IV : CI, [N_{SU}, K_{IV}]K_{TA}[N_{IV}, K_{SI}]K_{IV} \quad \text{--(xv)}$$

After IV receives the message, it decrypts the portion encrypted with K_{IV} , thereby obtaining the secret session key K_{SI} . It then forwards the relevant part of the message intended for SU, as follows:

$$IV \rightarrow SU : CI, [N_{SU}, K_{SI}]K_{TA} \quad \text{--(xvi)}$$

After completing the protocol run, both communicating parties SU and IV receive the shared secret key K_{SI} and do the transmission securely. The authentication messages from both correspondents are symmetric, allowing either party to initiate re-authentication and key change. When a correspondent discards a secret session key, the entire protocol must be play again because authentication replay messages cannot be reused. This ensures the protocol's resilience against replay attacks.

The discussed protocol is susceptible to MITM attack, as discussed by Frédéric Massicotte in [14]. He suggested that if an attacker copies SU to IV and vice versa, without either realizing it, a MITM attack might be executed with tools such as Hunt-type software [15].

Below are the steps to take advantage of this weakness are as under:

While SU begins a communication by transmitting message to IV, the attacker intercepts that message as under:

$$SU \rightarrow CI(IV) : CI, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}[N_{SU}, CI, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]K_{SU} \quad \text{-- (xvii)}$$

The intruder intercepts and retrieves this message (xvii), concatenates the encrypted portion with the identifier for conversation CI, and delivers it back to SU as under:

$$CI(IV) \rightarrow SU : CI, [N_{SU}, CI, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]K_{TA} \quad \text{--(xviii)}$$

When SU accepts this message, it validates the identifier for conversation and decrypts the encoded portion using its secret session key shared with TA. Upon successful decryption, it checks the correctness of nonce N_{SU} , confirming that the second part of the message (CI, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}) is indeed the secret session key. Since this information is transmitted in plaintext, an intruder could intercept and steal the session key. This attack does not require the intruder to complete the two protocol steps—messages from IV to TA and TA to IV.

B. Proposed MORNES Protocol

The proposed MORNeS protocol uses the following conventions:

- SU and IV: Communicating parties with SU initiating communication.

- MTA: MORNeS Trusted Authority
- CI: Cyber Intruder
- CI(IV): Cyber Intruder impersonating IV
- IF_{SU} , IF_{IV} : Identifiers of parties SU and IV, respectively.
- N_{SU} , N_{IV} : Nonces generated by parties SU and IV, respectively.
- K_{SM} : Mutual Secret keys among SU and MTA
- K_{IM} : Mutual Secret keys among IV and MTA
- K_{SI} : Mutual Secret keys among SU and IV

The MORNeS protocol operates as follows:

- If SU intends to initiate communication with IV, it transmits a message to IV having its identifier (IF_{SU}), IV's identifier (IF_{IV}), and an encoded message via the secret key allocated between SU and MTA (K_{SM}). The coded message includes a nonce (N_{SU}) generated by SU for current transmission session, along with IF_{SU} and IF_{IV} .
- IV, after receiving this message, a nonce N_{IV} generated specific for current transmission session. It combines N_{IV} with IF_{SU} and IF_{IV} , encrypts this combination using the secret key shared between IV and MTA (K_{IM}), and appends the encrypted result to the message received from SU. IV then sends this concatenated message to MTA.
- MTA decrypts the two encoded parts of the communication via K_{SM} and K_{IM} , respectively, and verifies them with IF_{SU} , IF_{IV} . Upon successful verification, MTA creates a session key K_{SI} to be assigned between the interactive parties SU and IV. It then makes two messages containing N_{SU} , N_{IV} , and K_{SI} . The first message is encrypted with K_{SM} and the second with K_{IM} . MTA concatenates these encrypted messages and sends them to IV.
- When IV gets this message, it decodes the portion encoded with K_{IM} to extract the nonces and session key. IV verifies N_{IV} to ensure the session key intended for the current message session. IV then encodes the previously recovered nonce N_{SU} via the session key K_{SI} . Afterward, IV concatenates the encoded N_{SU} with the piece of the message collected from MTA (coded using K_{SM}) and sends it to SU.
- When SU gets this message, it decodes the portion of the message using K_{SM} to extract the nonces and session key. Then, SU took the session key to decrypt another part of the message to retrieve N_{SU} , thereby confirming that the message is from IV and that the session key is for the exact transmission session. To create the identity to IV, SU encodes N_{IV} via the secret key K_{SI} and sends the message to IV.
- When IV gets this message, it decodes the portion of the message using K_{SI} and confirms the successful transmission of session key to SU. SU and IV can then communicate securely over the insecure network using the session key K_{SI} as established by the protocol above.

Using session key K_{SI} , SU and IV can communicate securely over the insecure network using the above protocol.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION, RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. PLAN FOR IMPLEMENTATION

The operation of the MORNeS protocol is illustrated in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Functionality of the MORNeS protocol

Below are the steps for MORNeS protocol for protected key interchange between SU and IV and mutual authentication as in the Table 1:

TABLE 1. MORNES PROTOCOL

S. No.	Communicating Parties	Message Transmitted
1.	SU → IV	$IF_{SU}, IF_{IV} [N_{SU}, CI, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]_{K_{SM}}$
2.	IV → MTA	$IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}, [N_{SU}, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]_{K_{SM}}, [N_{IV}, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]_{K_{IM}}$
3.	MTA → IV	$[N_{SU}, K_{IV}, K_{SI}]_{K_{SM}}, [N_{IV}, K_{SI}]_{K_{IM}}$
4.	IV → SU	$[N_{SU}, N_{IV} K_{SI}]_{K_{SM}}, [N_{SU}], K_{SI}$
5.	SU → IV	$[N_{IV}]_{K_{SI}}$

B. PROOF OF SECURITY

When an intruder records a message or a part of it received from earlier protocol execution, a replay attack occurs which replays it during the following protocol execution [16].

To demonstrate MORNeS's resilience against replay attacks, consider an example where an attacker attempts to interrupt the key interchange between SU and IV.

When SU initiates communication with IV as per the described protocol, a cyber attacker (CA) intercepts and copies the message delivered from IV to MTA in step 2. The intruder remains passive during the third step but intervenes during the fourth step to replay the copied message, impersonating IV in a replay attack.

After receiving the request, MTA creates a new key K_{SI} and delivers it to IV. This message is intercepted by CA, who further encoded the message holding the new key K_{SI} established from MTA to SU, along with the encrypted message containing N_{SU} received from IV.

SU attempts mutual authentication by attempting to decrypt N_{SU} using K_{SI} , which fails since N_{SU} was encrypted by IV using K_{SI} .

Additionally, SU encrypts N_{SU} using K_{SI} and sends it to IV, who is unable to decrypt it because it was encrypted using K_{SI} .

As a result, shared verification fails, and together SU and IV become informed of the communication invasion, leading to the key being removed.

The steps demonstrating security against replay attacks are outlined in Table 2

TABLE 2: SECURITY AGAINST REPLAY ATTACKS

S. No.	Communicating Parties	Message Transmitted
1.	SU → IV	$IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}[N_{SU}, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]K_{SM}$
2.	IV → MTA	$IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}, [N_{SU}, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]K_{SM}, [N_{IV}, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]K_{IM}$
This message is copied by the cyber attacker.		
3.	MTA → IV	$[N_{SU}, K_{IV}, K_{SI}]K_{SM}, [N_{IV}, N_{SU}, K_{SI}]K_{IM}$
4.	IV → SU	$[N_{SU}, N_{IV}K_{SI}]K_{SM}, [N_{SU}]K_{SI}$
This message is intercepted by the cyber attacker.		
5.	I(IV) → MTA	$IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}, [N_{SU}, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}], K_{SM}[N_{IV}, IF_{SU}, IF_{IV}]K_{IM}$
Cyber attacker replays the message copied in step 2.		
6.	MTA → IV	$[N_{SU}, N_{IV}, K_{SI}]K_{SM}, [N_{IV}, N_{SU}, K_{SI}]K_{IM}$
The server generates a new key, K_{SI} , in response to the replayed message. The intruder interrupt and duplicates this message		
7.	I(IV) → SU	$[N_{SU}, N_{IV}K_{SI}]K_{SM}, [N_{SU}]K_{SI}$
The attacker forwards the components of the message received via MTA and IV to SU, masquerading IV		
8.	SU → IV	$[N_{IV}] K_{SI}$
The mutual authentication fails because neither SU nor IV can decrypt the nonces.		

V. CONCLUSION

MORNeS protocol remains evaluated against the Key Interchange protocol introduced by Otway and Rees, focusing on their effectiveness in distributed computing environments. The performance metrics considered include:

- Encoding time for each block: t_e
- Decoding time for each block: t_d
- Transmission time for each block: t_t
- Nonce Generation time: t_n
- Session key generation time: t_{sk}

The computation of the operating time of Key Interchange protocol purported by Otway and Rees can be found in Table 3:

TABLE 3: OPERATING TIME OF KEY INTERCHANGE PROTOCOL PURPORTED BY OTWAY AND REES

S. No.	Location	Time
1	At SU	$t_n + 3t_e$
2	Transmission from SU to IV	$8t_t$
3	At IV	$2t_n + 4t_e$
4	Transmission from IV to TA	$9t_t$
5	At TA	$3t_d + 3t_d + 2t_{sk} + 4t_e + 4t_e$
6	Transmission from TA to IV	$5t_t$
7	At IV	$3t_d$
8	Transmission from IV to SU	$5t_t$
9	At SU	$3t_d$

Total running time

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= t_n + 3t_e + 8t_t + 2t_n + 4t_e + 9t_t + 3t_d + 3t_d + 2t_{sk} + 4t_e + 4t_e + 5t_t + 3t_d + 5t_t + 3t_d \\
 &= (1 + 2)t_n + (3 + 4 + 4 + 4)t_e + (8 + 9 + 5 + 5)t_t + (3 + 3 + 3 + 3)t_d + 2t_{sk} \\
 &= 3t_n + 15t_e + 27t_t + 12t_d + 2t_{sk}
 \end{aligned}$$

Likewise, the computation of the running time for the projected protocol MORNeS can be found in Table 4.

TABLE 4: RUNNING TIME OF PROJECTED PROTOCOL MORNES

S. No.	Location	Time
1	At SU	$2t_n + 3t_e$
2	Transmission from SU to IV	$6t_t$
3	At IV	$t_n + 4t_e$
4	Transmission from IV to TA	$7t_t$
5	At TA	$5t_d + 2t_{sk} + 5t_e$
6	Transmission from TA to IV	$7t_t$
7	At IV	$4t_d + t_e$
8	Transmission from IV to SU	$4t_t$
9	At SU	$3t_d + t_e$
10	Transmission from SU to IV	t_t

Total running time:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 2t_n + 3t_e + 6t_t + t_n + 4t_e + 7t_t + 5t_d + 2t_{sk} + 5t_e + 7t_t + 4t_d + t_e + 4t_t + 3t_d + t_e + t_t \\
 &= (2 + 1)t_n + (3 + 4 + 5 + 1 + 1)t_e + (6 + 7 + 7 + 4 + 1)t_t + (5 + 4 + 3)t_d + 2t_{sk} \\
 &= 3t_n + 14t_e + 25t_t + 12t_d + 2t_{sk}
 \end{aligned}$$

The operating time of Key Interchange protocol purported by Otway and Rees:

$$3t_n + 15t_e + 27t_t + 12t_d + 2t_{sk} \quad \text{--(xix)}$$

Running Time of projected protocol MORNeS:

$$3t_n + 14t_e + 25t_t + 12t_d + 2t_{sk} \quad \text{--(xx)}$$

By subtracting $3t_n + 12t_d + 2t_{sk}$ from equation (xix) and (xx) to exclude the common expressions, we find

$$15t_e + 27t_t \quad \text{--(xxi)}$$

$$14t_e + 25t_t \quad \text{--(xxii)}$$

The simplified equations for comparative analysis depend exclusively on t_e and t_t . Given the criticality of transmission time in distributed environments, the encryption process is significantly faster compared to transmission time, specifically t_e being much less than t_t ($t_e \ll t_t$).

Hence, t_e can be ignored in equations (xxi) and (xxii) derived earlier. Consequently, the relationship simplifies to a linear expression that illustrates complexity exclusively as a function of transmission time t_t

As the transmission time t_t increases, complexity of the protocol also increases.

→ $27 t_t$ --(xxiii)

→ $25 t_t$ --(xxiv)

The calculation of efficiency for MORNeS protocol (in percentage) as compared to key interchange protocol purported by Otway and Rees is calculated as follows:

$$\epsilon = \left\{ \left(\frac{27t_t - 25t_t}{25t_t} \right) \times 100 \right\} \%$$

$$\epsilon = \left\{ \left(\frac{2t_t}{25t_t} \right) \times 100 \right\} \%$$

$$\epsilon = 8 \%$$

Therefore, it can be said that the MORNeS protocol is 8% more efficient than Otway and Rees' key exchange protocol.

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